

PARLIAMENT
OF THE REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

THE SOUTH AFRICAN WILDLIFE ECONOMY

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Conservation of wildlife is frequently seen as a cost to governments, resulting in little investment in wildlife resources despite the extensive contributions that the wildlife economy can, and does, make in terms of employment and revenues. The wildlife economy has the potential to significantly increase employment above the current 410 000 jobs related to biodiversity. A biodiversity economy can generate jobs in line with other sectors in the national economy and improve citizens' welfare. South Africa's growing size of protected areas is an opportunity to expand grounds for biodiversity that fuels tourism and rural development. Communities need to be central in developing the biodiversity economy to enhance stakeholder relations and protect wildlife from illegal harvesting or poaching. Capacitation of communities could help solve governance problems, corruption, and conflicts that are often coupled with growing illicit wildlife trade and poverty issues. Illegal wildlife trade is the fourth largest transnational criminal activity globally and is driven by growing demand from Asia, thus putting pressure on populations of wildlife. Parliament is best placed to conduct oversight of Government plans to transform the wildlife sector to make it inclusive to address poverty, unemployment, and inequality.

1 INTRODUCTION

South Africa is the world's third most biologically diverse country and has a significant comparative advantage. The country is home to six per cent of the world's known plant species and fifteen per cent of all known coastal marine species. Current statistics have the number of South African animal species estimated at 67 000, while 20 401 plant species have been described.¹⁶ In terms of biomes, South Africa has nine unique vegetation types, of which three have been declared global biodiversity hotspots. It is the only country to contain an entire floral kingdom – the Cape Floral Region. South Africa's natural capital of biological diversity, combined with its wealth of indigenous knowledge, forms one of the country's greatest assets. The country is yet to fully exploit the vast biological assets for social and economic purposes.⁸ The natural capital could prove vital in the resuscitation of the struggling economy and create sustainable jobs, particularly in rural communities. The natural assets can provide raw materials for the natural product sector that requires fewer inputs and has high potential. More advanced economic activities could include bioprospecting for the development of pharmaceutical, cosmeceutical or industrial applications from compounds found in plants, animals and microorganisms. The assets could play a critical role in improving food and nutrition security from a variety of indigenous edible plants and animals.

South Africa is a host to 6% of global plant species

Reptiles
•404 species

Amphibians
•125 species

Mammals
•336 species

Birds
•732 species

Freshwater fish
•568 species

Marine fish
•13 000 species

Figure 1. The endowment of some animal species that South Africa enjoys.

South Africa has a demonstrable record of endorsing and practising biodiversity conservation and has a suite of policies toward wildlife management. These have enabled the growth of a substantial and innovative wildlife industry, tours and lodging.

Despite these observed growth factors in terms of governance, economic contribution and contribution to rural livelihoods, the natural resources face increasing threats from human-driven activities. There is growing competition and conflicts among sectors involving tourism, agriculture, mining, and biodiversity protection. These are becoming increasingly acute as natural resources are under pressure. Additionally, the wildlife sector has remained stubbornly untransformed for various reasons that will be discussed in this paper.

The purpose of the paper is to provide Members of Parliament with a review of performance, potential, and areas that require attention to enhance the wildlife sector's economic contribution. The ultimate goal is for Members to encourage more public and private investments in protected and conserved areas to improve biodiversity outcomes and support economic development, particularly in rural areas. The paper reflects on the marine and terrestrial environments being strategic components of the wildlife economy. It concludes by making recommendations for consideration by Parliament to be used for oversight purpose on the work of the Department of Environment, Forestry and Fisheries (hereafter referred to as the Department) and its associated entities.

2 OVERVIEW OF THE WILDLIFE ECONOMY

The definition of wildlife economy is evolving and expanding to include newer modes. It is accepted that the wildlife economy uses wildlife, plants and animals (marine and terrestrial) as an economic asset to create value that aligns with conservation objectives and delivers sustainable growth and economic development. The term biodiversity economy is also used interchangeably with wildlife economy in South Africa, particularly in official documents. The Government focuses on the five main wildlife economy activities: ecotourism, hunting, wildlife ranching, carbon finance and non-timber forest products. These activities contribute to both biodiversity conservation, social and economic development. Below is a brief description of the key wildlife economy activities:

- Ecotourism - includes non-consumptive tourism related to nature/wildlife.
- Hunting - includes trophy hunting, game meat hunting, and some aspects of fishing, such as artisanal, small-scale and recreational fishing.
- Wildlife ranching - includes breeding wild/indigenous animals for hunting, game meat, products, and other uses.
- Other consumptive use - includes non-timber forest products used commercially and for subsistence purposes.
- The carbon market - includes projects that earn income through REDD+ and other mechanisms that sequester carbon, reduce greenhouse gas emissions and conserve/preserve carbon's natural systems.

Economics prescribe that wildlife should be harvested as long as the marginal social benefits exceed the marginal social costs. Included in (marginal) benefits are values of wildlife products (e.g., caviar, medicinal plants, ivory, bush meat, hides) or the live specimen (if sold to a zoo or herbarium). Also, (marginal) social costs include (i) the loss

in situ (existence, viewing) value that wildlife provide citizens who may be located in countries other than the source country, (ii) the opportunity cost from harvesting the wildlife today rather than waiting for a more suitable time in the future when the specimen(s) may fetch a higher price, (iii) the lost future value of offspring that might result from leaving the specimen(s) in place, and (iv) the opportunity cost of the resources employed in the harvest activity.²

The economic contribution of biodiversity is linked to the national economic performance of the country. As much as the economy is diversified, it has been struggling to grow closer to its potential in recent years. Before the COVID-19 outbreak, the economy grew around 1 per cent, with manufacturing making up the most considerable contribution.^{14, 21} However, the economic growth has not translated to the reduction of unemployment, inequality and poverty. During quarter 4 of 2020, unemployment stood at 32.5 per cent, while more than 14 million South African lived below the food poverty line. Women remain more disadvantaged than men, consistently recording a higher headcount, gap and severity measures at each point in time of data collection. However, the difference between the sexes is narrowing.^{20,}

²¹

The biodiversity sector promises to provide more sustainable jobs, create opportunities for previously disadvantaged individuals and further open the sector even though it is affected by national developments. Many biodiversity-related jobs are outside the urban centres and are labour intensive, contributing to rural development, poverty alleviation, inclusive growth and labour absorption. Biodiversity-based tourism is regarded as a significant growth area. In 2015, this sector accounted for more than 88 000 direct jobs and generated a direct spend of over R30 billion in the South African economy.¹ National tourism and economic growth strategies should incorporate biodiversity-based tourism as an area for targeted investment. Jobs directly related to biodiversity total more than 418 000, and this is likely an underestimate. This level of employment is comparable to that of the mining sector, which employs 434 000 people. For each job created and dedicated to protecting biodiversity, there are five jobs that directly depend on biodiversity.¹⁶

Tourism has been hailed as the fast-growing sector that contributes significantly to the country's gross domestic product (GDP). The heartbeat of tourism is wildlife. Some refer to wildlife as the oil that runs the tourism engine. In 2018, tourism contributed R130 billion to the country's GDP - accounting for 2.8 per cent of real GDP and it is estimated that 64 per cent of visitors are wildlife tourists.¹⁹ It is equally valid that the wildlife economy thrives because of tourism. The wildlife economy in South Africa has been growing consistently faster than the general economy, contributing R3 billion million to GDP in 2014 – almost double the sector's contribution in 2008.¹ However, it is unclear how resilient these growth rates are to market distresses, and as mentioned earlier, national accounting for the wildlife economy is still being developed. It requires improvements to capture the value of the wildlife economy fully. The available statistics are often contradictory and far from each other when comparing the subsectors of wildlife economy.

Hunting is one of the most significant revenue contributors to the wildlife industry, where 85 per cent of hunting revenues come from domestic hunters, primarily for meat/biltong. In 2018, local hunters contributed approximately R10.1 billion and foreign hunters about R1.8 billion, providing an estimated total of R11.9 billion.²⁴ The Biodiversity Economy Strategy (BES) has set an industry growth goal stating that by 2030, the South African biodiversity economy will achieve an average annualised GDP growth rate of 10 per cent per annum.⁸ This envisioned growth curve extends into the year 2030 and is aligned to the country's National Development Plan (NDP), Vision 2030, and commitments under the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Cooperation between the private sector, Government and communities will firstly catalyse growth in the sector. Secondly, growth will be realised through opportunities in various market segments and addressing associated development and growth constraints. The cornerstone for growth is managing both the wildlife and bioprospecting industries in an environmentally sustainable manner. This growth would not only support returns on investment for existing investors but would also enable new investments in support of South Africa's economic transformation.

3 DOMESTICATION OF INTERNATIONAL AGREEMENTS THAT AFFECT WILDLIFE ECONOMY

This section reflects on the alignment of domestic tools with international commitments on wildlife. South Africa is a member of numerous protocols, agreements and statutes that affect the state of wildlife. The section is limited to two central biodiversity instruments that directly affect the wildlife economy.

3.1 Convention on Biological Diversity

South Africa ratified the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) in 1997, endorsing the Convention's objectives, including the mainstreaming of biodiversity in all governmental policies, plans and programmes. Mainstreaming refers to integrating or inclusion of actions related to conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity in government policies and strategies relating to business sectors, such as agriculture, fisheries, forestry, tourism and mining. Within the context of the South African economy's transformation, mainstreaming refers to the inclusion of biodiversity considerations in poverty reduction plans and national sustainable development plans.

The White Paper on Sustainable Use of South Africa's Biological Diversity, developed in 1997, set out several goals, strategies and priorities for conservation, sustainable use and equitable benefit sharing. Article 6b of the CBD prescribes that the Parties have an obligation to "Integrate, as far as possible and as appropriate, the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity into relevant sectoral or cross-sectoral plans, programmes and policies." The need to mainstream the conservation and sustainable use of biological resources across all sectors of the national economy, society and the policy-making framework is a complex challenge at the heart of the Convention.

During the 2010 CBD conference, signatories adopted the Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and the Aichi Biodiversity Targets. The Strategic Plan focuses on five strategic goals composed of twenty targets that are to be achieved either by 2015 or 2020. The Strategic goals are to:

- Address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss by mainstreaming biodiversity across Government and society.
- Reduce the direct pressures on biodiversity and promote sustainable use.
- Improve the status of biodiversity by safeguarding ecosystems, species and genetic diversity.
- Enhance the benefits to all from biodiversity and ecosystem services.
- Enhance implementation through participatory planning, knowledge management and capacity building.

The contracting parties to the CBD are obligated to develop and implement National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP). An NBSAP sets out an integrated, coherent national strategy for the conservation, management, and sustainable use of biodiversity and explicitly outlines how contracting parties will achieve the Convention's objectives. It also provides a framework for integrating biodiversity considerations into other sectoral plans and strategies, and as such, is a critical mainstreaming tool.

South Africa developed its first NBSAP in 2005, which is integrated into national development and sectoral planning frameworks. In 2005, South Africa's policy and legislative framework for the conservation, management and sustainable use of biodiversity was already well developed. The strategy was updated in 2015 to cover the 2015-2025 implementation period.⁷ The NBSAP makes explicit links to the priorities and strategies of a wide range of role players and sectors. Implementing the plan is part of the country's efforts to mainstream and enhance the profile and value proposition of biodiversity and ecosystem services across sectors. However, more than awareness raising and profile enhancement, mainstreaming has the potential of significantly improving the implementation of biodiversity requirements, as reflected in the CBD strategic plan, and the achievement of the Aichi biodiversity targets, without potentially compromising the identity of the sector. Having made significant progress on mainstreaming as reported in the sixth National Report, NDP and the recently adopted SDGs, South Africa considers mainstreaming as a strategic priority to effect changes at the policy and institutional levels to fast track progress towards achievement of the Aichi Biodiversity Targets.

In 2010, in line with the CBD commitments, South Africa endorsed and updated Strategy for Plant Conservation, which aligns with the 2011-2020 Global Strategy for Plant Conservation (GSPC). This strategy responds to the South African Government's priorities, such as job creation through research projects on how to grow medicinal plants on a national scale and promote a healthy environment for all people, one of the fundamental rights outlined in the Constitution (Figure 2). Without the availability of medicinal plants, the Government would need a significant increase in fiscal spending on health care.¹⁷ The demand and use of medicinal plants increased since the outbreak of COVID-19.¹⁰ Maintaining ecological infrastructure and resources through protection and restoration of threatened ecosystems needs to be prioritised to minimise adverse health impacts.

Figure 2 Medicinal plants that more than 85 per cent of South Africans use from the wild.

The fifth Global Biodiversity Outlook (GBO) provides a global summary of progress towards the Aichi Biodiversity Targets and is based on a range of indicators, research studies and assessments (in particular the IPBES Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services), as well as the national reports provided by countries on their implementation of the CBD. According to the report, none of the Aichi Biodiversity Targets was fully met, while six targets were partially achieved. The non-delivery against the targets is threatens the SDGs' achievement and undermines efforts to address climate change.³ The South African National Biodiversity Assessment shows that biodiversity's significant challenges are habitat loss, changes to freshwater flow, overuse of some species, pollution, climate change, and invasive alien species.¹⁶ The assessment report reflects on the Aichi Targets and areas that need more effort. These shortcoming areas are essential for monitoring as part of oversight.

3.2 The Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora

South Africa is a party to the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), an agreement between governments. The agreement aims to ensure that international trade in wild animals and plants' specimens does not threaten their survival. The primary mode of operation is the prevention of illegal trade or trans-shipment through non-parties. The second area is the promotion of compliance with and enforcement of the requirements of the Convention. The Convention assist parties to take action against non-compliance. The use of CITES to block trade in illegally caught animals and animal products have proven to be less

effective for the South African case. Rhino, abalone and elephant poaching demand has remained stubbornly high. Since 1977, all rhino species have been in Appendix I^a of CITES, which prohibits international commercial trade in rhinos and their products and derivatives, including hunting trophies. In 1994, the White Rhino population of South Africa was listed in Appendix II, which allows regulated trade. The controversial aspect of regulated trade is how certain animals are viewed in society. For example, there is opposition and disapproval to farming and trade in big cats or their derivatives on animal welfare grounds. At the same time, there is acceptance of trade in other animal groups.

Following the decision to list rhinos, the number of White Rhinos auctioned, sport-hunted and poached in South Africa increased steadily. Poached rhinos peaked in 2014 at 1 250. After that, there was a gradual decline in the numbers of poached rhinos to 394 in 2020. The low 2020 poaching statistics can be attributed to the nationwide lockdowns to curb the spread of COVID-19. The movement of poachers and rhino horn smugglers was curtailed, hence the 33 per cent decrease when compared to the 594 killed in 2019. The decline marks the sixth year that rhino poaching has continued to decrease in South Africa.⁵ The wildlife losses in South Africa continue to drive the escalating trend with record poaching deaths in the region. When an adult female rhino is killed, the calf often dies afterwards. Hence the killing a female rhino is a more severe crime than killing a male rhino. The loss of a female rhino also means the loss of 10 calves that she was going to produce at her lifetime.⁶ High prices in illegal Asian markets, criminality in the wildlife industry, government policy lapses and occasional complicity, and Asian-run criminal syndicates stand behind the continuing attrition in South Africa.¹³

Combatting poaching and wildlife trafficking is not only an international obligation under the CITES, but also a national imperative because it is also a security threat. Wildlife crimes are primarily organised crime that requires an inter-departmental approach assisted by civil society. The draft National Integrated Strategy to Combat Wildlife Trafficking (NISCWT) was borne out of those collaborations and their associated deliverables and timelines.¹⁸ The strategy revolves around the capacitation of law enforcement to improve outcomes in the justice system that will serve as a deterrent. The other angle is enhancing the capacity for detection and preventative measures. The strategy is yet to be finalised, and its timelines have passed since most targets were for implementation by 2020. Parliament may need to be updated on the milestones and medium to long term goals.

4 KEY LEGISLATION AND POLICY FRAMEWORKS

Wildlife policies are typically driven by the state of wildlife species as a factor of a threat from agricultural, fisheries or forestry production, or by the species providing benefits with public good characteristics, such as when the species is threatened, and

^a Appendix I includes species threatened with extinction. Trade in specimens of these species is permitted only in exceptional circumstances. Appendix II includes species not necessarily threatened with extinction, but in which trade must be controlled in order to avoid utilisation incompatible with their survival. Appendix III contains species that are protected in at least one country.

its preservation is considered highly valuable. In principle, externality problems can be solved if all stakeholders cooperate, which has proven successful for natural resource management in relatively small communities¹². There is a large body of literature on voluntary cooperation in managing natural resources such as in fisheries. However, literature is still sparse on the successful application of co-management principles to wildlife resources. In instances where traditional management of resources are seen to be failing, and there is no successful voluntary cooperation among role players, the Government has to intervene, often with coercive power, for improved management.

South Africa has a firm policy and legislative framework for the conservation, management and sustainable use of biodiversity (Figure 3). The overall framework for environmental governance in South Africa is established in the Constitution of the Republic of South Africa⁹, which:

- Protects the “right to an environment that is not harmful to health and well-being^b”;
- Balances the right to have the environment protected with rights to valid social and economic development^c; and
- Allocates environmental functions to a wide range of government agencies in all spheres and requiring cooperation between government agencies and spheres of Government^d.

Chapter 3 of the Constitution establishes of the three spheres of Government in South Africa – national, provincial and local. They operate as “distinctive, interdependent and interrelated” spheres of Government through co-operative governance, a principle emphasised in the Constitution. The Constitution also outlines certain national legislative competencies, which include land reform, water resources, forest resources, marine resources, national parks and national botanical gardens. Functional areas of concurrent national and provincial legislative competence outlined in the Constitution include environmental management, pollution control, soil conservation, nature conservation (excluding national parks, national botanical gardens and marine resources) and regional planning and development. Local government (district and local municipalities) play an essential role in developing and managing biodiversity in the National Environmental Management Act (Act 107 of 1998). Key legislation is highlighted in Figure 3 below. The critical State institutions responsible for driving the wildlife economy are the South African National Parks Authority (SANParks) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI).

The South African Government has identified, through Operation Phakisa, the need to establish a Lab focusing on the biodiversity economy. The Operation Phakisa on Biodiversity Lab was thus launched to fast-track delivery on the biodiversity economy.²² It is worth mentioning that before establishing the Biodiversity Lab, there was a South African Wildlife Forum. The Forum was established in 2006 to create a platform for constructive interaction between the Government and the wildlife sector. The Wildlife

^b Section 24a

^c Section 24b

^d Section 99

Forum was repositioned as one of the Biodiversity Economic Lab outcomes to facilitate the advancement of transformation and economic growth. The second goal is to promote the sustainable utilisation of indigenous biological resources and create an enabling environment to achieve these outcomes. The two streams from the Lab are bioprospecting and wildlife. Bioprospecting focuses on the commercialisation of indigenous species, while the wildlife stream seeks to develop the entire chain and support services in wildlife farming or ranching. The 2020 targets were the creation of 24 800 jobs and adding R1.9 billion to the economy through supporting 4 500 small, micro and medium businesses. It is likely that the COVID-19 outbreak affected the achievement of this target. The 2030 targets are 100 000 jobs in the sector, wherein 30 per cent of wildlife businesses will be Black-owned. The area managed by Black-operators will be more than 10 million hectares (ha), either in the form of ranches or game farms. The 2030 targets may need to be revised. However, Parliament must stay abreast of the delivery regarding transformation.

Figure 3. The list of key legislation, policies or strategies that have a direct bearing on wildlife economy

Implementing the conservation legislation has increased the number and coverage of protected areas to enhance socio-economic value and benefits from biodiversity in the country (Figure 4). Protected areas are essential not only for protecting ecosystems and species but also for social and economic development, especially in rural areas. Protected areas are vital for ecological sustainability and climate change adaptation.¹⁶ The National Biodiversity Economy Strategy (NBES) states that the biodiversity economy encompasses the businesses and economic activities that either directly depends on biodiversity for their core business or that contribute to the conservation of biodiversity through their activities⁸.

NBES has the following principles:

- Conservation of biodiversity and ecological infrastructure
- Sustainable use of indigenous resources
- Fair and equitable beneficiation
- Socio-economic sustainability
- Incentive-driven compliance with regulation
- Ethical practices
- Improving the quality and standards of products

Figure 4 The extent of declared protected areas in South Africa.¹

5 COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES AND CHALLENGES IN THE SECTOR

5.1 Advantages and opportunities

South Africa has a competitive hunting offering compared to other African countries such as Botswana, Namibia, Mozambique, Tanzania and Zimbabwe, as the country has a wide variety of game, and is known as an excellent destination for 'combo' trips – combining hunting, fishing and safari activities. However, hunting the “Big Five” is relatively expensive in South Africa (only in Namibia is the cost slightly higher), and regulations on firearms and trophy exports are considered to be challenging.⁸ When hunting takes place on ranches, on average, the hunting areas tend to be smaller because of the requirement for fencing, which can also increase the costs. Social pressure in source markets against hunting also creates an additional challenge.¹

While South Africa remains well-endowed in various plant species, there are ongoing threats to the existing plant communities. Many plant species, communities and their ecological interactions, including the many relationships between plant species and human communities and cultures, are in danger of extinction. Human-induced factors such as habitat loss and transformation, over-exploitation, pollution, clearing for development activities, alien invasive species and climate change threaten species with extinction. If this loss is not stemmed, countless opportunities to develop new solutions to pressing economic, social, health and industrial problems will be equally lost. Furthermore, plant diversity is of particular concern to indigenous and local communities, and these communities have a vital role to play in addressing the loss of plant diversity.

According to the Department, the biodiversity economy is an ideal development and transformation sector in the South African context for several reasons:

- A strong and growing domestic and international demand for the products and services produced by this sector exists.
- It realises the economic value of indigenous species and, in many cases, indigenous/traditional knowledge.
- It facilitates rural economic development.
- It has very high value-add potential.
- It has a high potential to earn foreign currency.
- It enables the development of new product markets.
- Wildlife has a comparative advantage in drylands because agriculture output has been declining.

The implementation of SANParks' Wildlife Economy Programme is an effort to redress the historical exclusion of Black people from the game farming industry by creating opportunities where local communities and emerging game farmers can establish their own wildlife enterprises. This redress is achieved through mechanisms for the transparent and equitable supply of founder herds of game to applicants whilst raising awareness for conservation, protected area management and sustainable utilisation principles in the wildlife industry. SANParks Wildlife Economy Programme works through

wildlife donation or loans as informed by assessment criteria and background checks. Wildlife donation offers local communities the opportunity to own game and participate in the wildlife economy centred on game farming activities relating to stocking, breeding, trading, and related ecotourism activities. In contrast, wildlife loan helps emerging game farmers develop their skills and capacity to enter into and play a meaningful role in the wildlife economy. A recipient enters into a custodianship agreement with SANParks for three years. SANParks is also assisting in developing economic activities around wildlife, such as guesthouses, crafts and services for guests. While this programme unfolds, there are also fronting claims by established operators who use communities to bolster their existing operations. Fronting could dampen the efforts of transforming the sector.

5.2 Challenges

Communities allocated land under the land reform programme may not be classified under private property rights because the rights have many dependencies. In solving wildlife management challenges, literature shows two polar cases of wildlife ownership, public and private. The provision of private property rights to wildlife provides economic incentives for efficient management of wildlife populations, as it permits property owners to market wildlife in various ways.²³ Private property rights have proven successful in increasing the population of elephants in Zimbabwe and South Africa, where markets for ivory and hunting exist, but when such markets are not allowed or demand is limited, private property rights are insufficient to preserve valuable species.¹⁵ Another possible reason for the failure of private property rights is wildlife species migration, which implies that habitat management by one landowner could positively affect wildlife abundance on neighbouring land for which the landowner is not rewarded.²³ Further, private property rights to wildlife could be inefficient if there are high costs for monitoring, and hence a higher risk for illegal hunting, albeit we have not found studies on these topics. Costs of game animals include browsing, predation, traffic accidents, and transmission of diseases. Similar to benefit estimates, these costs are calculated for groups of individuals with and without dispersal effects into the rest of an economy. For each category, the costs consist of three parts: costs for actual damage, costs of mitigation, and costs for adaption measures.¹¹

The summary of the major challenges identified by the Biodiversity Economy Lab in the wildlife economy include:

- Lack of transformation of the biodiversity economy sector (due to barriers such as high capital costs), including game ranching, hunting and associated industries, biotrade and bioprospecting activities;
- Risk of future growth stagnation;
- An enabling environment that does not support the game meat industry;
- Skewed beneficiation from wildlife economy revenues;
- Insufficient funding and capacity for implementation of skills development, technology transfer and income-generating initiatives;
- Lack of available equipment and skills to engage in the biotechnology aspect of bioprospecting;

- The negative public opinion towards trophy hunting even when there are positive spin-offs that benefit communities; and
- Insufficient appreciation of the value and potential of the natural product sector in poverty alleviation

6 RECOMMENDATIONS AND ROLE OF PARLIAMENT

6.1 Recommendations

6.1.1 Community-based natural resource management

Top-down policy decisions to restrict the exploitation of resources can be counterproductive and does not encourage inventive buy-in from local people. It is costly to enforce prohibitions against local people's chosen activities, thus bans often increase monitoring costs without conservation benefits.^{4, 11} This is because the conversion of reserve lands and incursions for wildlife poaching halt when local people want it to do so, not when they are told to do so. The least costly policies provide incentives for the local people to support the reserve's designated uses, not bans against non-designated uses. Partnership with locals is the best tool in the conservation and wildlife economy.

6.1.2 Equitable quota schemes

Individually transferrable quota (ITQ^e) programmes provide incentives for self-enforcement among fishers because the value of an ITQ depends on the integrity of both the system design and its practice. Although individuals stand to gain by exceeding their quota, they are adversely affected if other quota owners do likewise. In general, if the fishery is overfished, the incomes of fishers are reduced, and the price of quotas will fall. If all fishers adhere to the rules, all should benefit in line with the quota they hold. A system of financial penalties often provides fishers with extra incentive to comply with their quota restrictions.² South Africa needs an equitable ITQ system for fisheries resources to be sustainably harvested.

6.1.3 Restrain mining on the marine ecosystem

The capacity of mineral development to contribute to biodiversity conservation is not intuitively obvious. Mining is an extractive industry and, by its very nature, can have significant direct and secondary environmental and social impacts. The harmful mining legacy of past practices has created a deep level of mistrust of the industry in conservation circles and raised questions about its role in society's transition to sustainable development. South Africa grapples with balancing socio-economic needs and environmental protection, and this issue has polarised society. Mining is also notorious for pollution on the terrestrial and marine environment. However, recent approvals for seabed and coastal prospecting is worrying fishers and environmental groups alike. Along the West Coast, diamond mining is already causing ecological

^e ITQ is a market-based fisheries management system that give fishermen quasi-private property rights over the resource and allow fishers to trade or exchange their allocation within defined limits.

harm by smothering the seabed and damaging the inshore reef systems.²⁵ Parliament should be actively involved in advocating for restraint and scrutiny when the Department processes mining applications on pristine and sensitive ecosystems.

6.1.4 *Climate change*

Climate change threatens the survival of wildlife, humans and the base ecosystem. Climate-smart conservation planning, sustainable natural resource management and conservation-friendly enterprises are powerful tools to reduce the vulnerability of communities in the face of climate shifts. The expansion of forests and forested areas could be a helpful climate change mitigation strategy that will enhance carbon sinks while also creating habitat for some species. Securing water resources will not only help communities but will equally help wildlife that shares the living space. Parliament should monitor the Department's reforestation and afforestation programme, particularly in areas affected by forest fires or high potential areas. Briefings should be held to ensure climate change readiness at district and municipal levels. A further discussion is required to address climate victims' slow compensation, which often takes more than two years.

6.2 Oversight role

- The Department should keep Parliament abreast of how costs are managed in new wildlife economy projects to keep the projects viable and profitable. Regular meetings should be convened to get updates on projects.
- Parliament should request regular briefings on the work of the Biodiversity Economy Lab under Operation Phakisa to ensure delivery on set objectives, particularly in aiding the recovery of the economy
- Air, land and water pollutants that cannot be seen, smelt or touched affect biodiversity. Parliament should encourage the Department to start monitoring critical pollutants in wildlife. Pollution may muddy landscapes, poison soils and waterways, or kill plants and animals. For humans, long-term exposure to air pollution, for example, can lead to chronic respiratory disease, lung cancer and other diseases. Very little monitoring of pollutants is ongoing for wildlife and its relations to extinctions.
- A sustainable wildlife economy benefits people and nature, using habitats and wildlife in an ecological, economic and socially sustainable way. Parliament should ensure regular reporting on socio-economic indicators for communities living closest to wildlife and their role and stake in managing nature.
- The Department should conduct an audit and set up mechanisms to root out any possible fronting in the wildlife sector.
- Parliament needs to be briefed on the steps that are taken to ensure that 100 million ha of wildlife economy is Black-owned and managed by 2030, including the support programmes.
- Parliament needs to take a resolute yet balanced decision on trophy hunting, particularly the farming and hunting of big cats.
- Parliament should ensure that the Department fast tracks the development of norms and standards to manage and mitigate critical wildlife economy risks,

such as intensive and selective breeding, animal diseases, intensive bioprospecting and invasive species.

- Parliament should encourage the expansion of wildlife in drylands because wildlife economies are more profitable than livestock rearing. Governments should establish support programmes for communities and invest in conserving wildlife, and wildlife-based markets.

7 CONCLUSION

The wildlife economy thrives from nature-based tourism. Tourism drives jobs and significant contributions to local economies, and revenues from safaris and other travel-related industries provide critical funding for wildlife protection and protected areas management. Wildlife conservation and expansion of protected areas are part of the implementation of the SDGs. Among countries that officially endorse a sustainable use approach to biodiversity conservation, South Africa stands out as a pioneer of market-friendly policies toward the wildlife economy. These have enabled a substantial and innovative wildlife ranching industry driven by private landowners and entrepreneurs. This industry not only contributes meaningfully to rural livelihoods and the country's economy, but it also appears to generate significant positive spillover effects for both landscape and species conservation. The industry needs close monitoring to transform in terms of composition and ownership. The ongoing controversy around trophy hunting has the potential to dent the hunting industry and associated economic benefits. Parliament thus needs to be decisive and assert its oversight role where there are elements of non-compliance with the resolutions on trophy hunting.

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